

EMPIRICAL EVALUATION OF OIL PRICE VOLATILITY AND STOCK MARKET RETURNS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study is on empirical evaluation of the impact of oil prices volatility on stock market returns in Nigeria. With the understanding that energy runs like a bloodstream of any business of which oil is a major source, it becomes imperative to examine the effects of incessant oil price fluctuations on critical indicators of the economy like stock market performance. The objectives include to; determine effects of oil price fluctuations on economic growth, ascertain the nexus trend between oil price volatility and stock market in Nigeria, and determine the impact of oil price volatility on the stock market returns in Nigeria. The scope of this study covers the period from 1986 to 2021. The work is based on secondary data sourced from UNCTAD; World Development Indicator (2021) and analysed with the aid of the software EVIEWS version 12. The study used the unit root test to check the stationarity of the variables, the ARDL bound test to check for long-term relationships between the variables, and the ARDL model to estimate both short- and long-term relationships between the variables. A normality test revealed that the study's variables are all typical. Breuseeh-Gdfrey serial correlation revealed no association between the study's variables. The heteroscedasticity test showed there was no outlier's effect on the output of the result. It was found that inflation and exchange rate volatility are positive and statistically significant; inflation and interest rate are equally positive related to private consumption during the period under investigation. It found out inflation, oil price, exchange rate, and real gross domestic product have positive effect on stock market performance in Nigeria. The work concludes oil price is a major determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. It was recommended that all brokerage firms and investment advisors need to conduct periodic research on macroeconomic environment and advise their clients accordingly on the best counters to invest in owing to the various influences by macroeconomic environment on the stock market performance.

Keywords: Oil, Prices, Volatility, Stock, Market, Returns

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Oil is a major source of energy globally and a crucial element of Nigeria's economy, significantly influencing its economic and political landscape. Although Nigeria's oil industry dates back to the early 20th century, it was not until after the Nigerian Civil War (1967-1970) that oil began to dominate the economic sphere. The discovery of crude oil has had both positive and negative impacts on Nigeria's economy.

The oil sector contributes approximately 90% of Nigeria's total revenue. It generates employment opportunities, boosts foreign exchange reserves, and supplies energy to various industries and commerce. Nigeria joined the

Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) in 1971 and established the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) in 1977, a state-controlled entity involved in both the upstream and downstream sectors (Blair, 1976).

Following the discovery of crude oil by Shell D'Arcy Petroleum, pioneer production commenced in 1958 from an oil field in Oloibiri, Eastern Niger Delta. By the late 1960s and early 1970s, Nigeria's crude oil production surpassed 2 million barrels per day, although it declined in the 1980s due to economic downturns.

On the negative side, oil exploitation has led to significant environmental degradation in surrounding communities. This has caused a loss of livelihood and other economic and social challenges. Despite NNPC's efforts to maximize capacity and improve petroleum product distribution, inefficiencies persist, leading to inconsistent supply and allocation issues.

Crude oil prices have experienced significant volatility over time. According to Olayungbo and Ojeyinka (2021), the first major global oil price shock occurred from 1973 to 1974, when prices surged from \$3 to \$12 per barrel due to the Arabian embargo. The second shock occurred between 1978 and 1979 during the Iranian Revolution, with prices rising from \$12 to \$18 per barrel. The third shock took place during the Iraq-Iran conflict (1980-1990), which saw oil prices increase from \$28 to \$40 per barrel. The 2008-2009 global financial crisis caused oil prices to plummet from \$100 to \$47 per barrel (Olayungbo & Ojeyinka, 2021).

The Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), established in 1960 and renamed in 1977, is a critical institution in Nigeria's capital market. It has branches in major cities, with its head office in Lagos and another office in Abuja (Akigbo, 1996). The NSE opened in 1961 with 19 listed equities. Today, it lists 328 securities with a total market value of approximately N28.26 trillion as of January 2020 (Akigbo, 1996). The NSE and the Securities & Exchange Commission (SEC), which enforces the Investments & Securities Decree 1999, regulate transactions on the Exchange.

The deregulation of Nigeria's capital market in 1993 and the repeal of foreign participation restrictions in 1995 allowed foreigners to engage as operators and investors. Since 1987, the NSE has been a part of the Reuters Electronic Contributor System, facilitating global distribution of stock market data, trade statistics, and company news.

The primary objectives of the NSE include developing a system for capital formation, offering efficient resource allocation, providing unique financing options, maintaining market discipline, and broadening share ownership (Akigbo, 1996). The influence of oil price volatility on the capital market is significant. Oil price fluctuations impact the stock market by reflecting the market's expectations of future profitability (Akigbo, 2014). The stock market absorbs the current and expected future impacts of oil price shocks, which are reflected in stock prices and returns.

The effect of oil price volatility on the economy is complex and unsettled, with no consensus on the relationship between financial variables and oil prices. Researchers like Salisu and Oloko (2015), Babatunde et al. (2013), and Fowowe (2013) argue that there is a direct relationship between oil prices and stock market performance. This study aims to link these variables, examining the impact of oil price volatility on stock market returns using disaggregated data.

The Nigerian Stock Exchange serves as a catalyst for mobilizing and utilizing private and public savings for productive uses (Akigbo, 1996). Fluctuations in oil prices can pose threats to the stock market, given the oil

industry's critical role in providing foreign exchange and total revenue for Nigeria's socio-political and economic wellbeing.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Oil discovery in Nigeria has driven economic growth and infrastructural development but has also caused significant environmental harm, particularly water pollution that has devastated aquatic life and stripped local fishermen of their livelihood. As a mono-economy heavily reliant on oil, Nigeria's macroeconomic stability is highly sensitive to fluctuations in oil demand and supply. The 1970s oil boom led to the neglect of non-oil revenues, an expanding public sector, and poor financial discipline, exposing Nigeria to oil price volatility and financial instability.

Efforts by various governments to revive agriculture and diversify the economy have included initiatives like Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), Green Revolution, and National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), along with others. Despite these efforts, the economy remains vulnerable. Nigeria's open economy is highly susceptible to crises, which significantly impact its volatile stock market, posing challenges for investors and financial analysts.

The Nigerian stock market experiences high volatility due to risks and price shocks. Risk-averse investors often avoid the market due to the uncertainty and volatility in expected returns (Kumeka et al., 2017). High volatility increases unfavorable market premiums, and investors demand higher returns on investments (Atoi, 2014). Oil price fluctuations induce large variations in stock market returns, making oil prices a significant concern for scholars. Most research focuses on developed economies, with limited studies on developing economies like Nigeria, despite its significant stock exchange.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this research study is to examine the causality between oil price volatility and stock market returns. In order to achieve the broad objectives, it is pertinent to streamline the specific objectives which are to:

- i. Determine effect of oil price fluctuation on the economic growth in Nigeria
- ii. Establish the nexus trend between oil price volatility and stock market in Nigeria.
- iii. Determine the impact of oil price volatility on stock market returns in Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

In line with the research objectives, the study aims to provide the answers to the following research questions.

- i. Does oil price volatility have an impact on stock market returns?
- ii. What is the effect of oil price fluctuation on the economic growth in Nigeria?
- iii. Is there any nexus between oil price fluctuations and economic growth in Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

To carry out this study, the following hypothesis has to be tested:

- H₀₁.** Oil price volatility has no significant impact on stock market returns.
- H₀₂.** There is no significant effect of oil price volatility on stock market returns.
- H₀₃.** There is no significant nexus of oil price fluctuation and economic growth.

1.6 Scope of the Study

This research study will focus on the oil price volatility effect and stock market returns in Nigeria from 1986-2021. The study starts in 1987 because there was a world stock market crash called 'black Monday' with worldwide losses of about US\$1.71trillion and this significantly affected the world's market, and it ends with

2021 because of the challenges in finding accurate and verified data. The study will not cover other African countries who may be facing similar challenges. But the findings of this study can be used as a guide.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Oil price changes affects numerous economic variables such as interest rates, investment decisions, economic growth, investors' confidence etc. these variables have been documented to affect both the stock market and exchange rate market (Hamilton, 1983; Amano & Van Norden, 1995). Again, oil prices are expressed in US dollars in the international market; hence, the dollar exchange rate may affect the price perceived by oil producing nations. Roubaud & Arouri, (2018). This study reviews the connection between these variables (Oil price, exchange rate and stock market returns) using a bivariate and multivariate approach. To some economists, there is a positive correlation between crude oil price and stock market performance (Cong, Weiy, Jiao & Fan, 2008; Boyer & Filion, 2007; Sadorsky, 2001).

According to Babatunde (2013) while the initial effects were contained due to low levels of exposure to complex financial instruments, the large swings in oil prices, combined with the resulting depreciation of the naira and drop in investor confidence led to growing pressures about the oil price volatility which was supported with exposure of oil subsidy frauds by importers of fuel products, who had a high foreign currency obligations owing to the high fuel prices in 2008, the subsequent falling oil prices and devaluations of naira added to the shocks experienced in the Nigerian stock market(Babatunde, 2013).

2.1.1 Oil Price and Exchange Rate

Theories generally posit that crude oil prices and exchange rates are positively correlated in oil-exporting countries, with higher crude oil prices leading to currency appreciation and vice versa. Crude oil price shocks affect exchange rates through two primary channels: the terms of trade channel and the wealth effect channel. The terms of trade channel suggests that a negative shock to the terms of trade drives down the price of non-tradable goods in the domestic economy, causing the real exchange rate in oil-exporting economies to depreciate and vice versa. The wealth effect channel indicates that a drop in crude oil prices results in losses for oil exporters but gains for oil importers, shifting current account balances and leading to portfolio reallocations between oil trading companies (Akigbo, 2014).

Adenekan (2020) states that a negative oil price shock transfers wealth from oil exporters to oil importers, or higher oil prices lead to higher production costs and inflation, which have contractionary effects on the economy and trade balances. To restore or improve trade balances, the exchange rate must adjust. The impact of oil prices on exchange rates can vary between advanced and emerging market economies (Adenekan, 2020).

Hamilton (2009) notes that oil price shocks respond directly to economic or geopolitical events and economic downturns (demand-side shocks). Supply-side shocks are driven by disruptions in oil production, such as the Iranian invasion of the U.S. embassy in 1978, the Iraq invasion of Kuwait in 1980, the Arab Spring in 2000, and the Iranian attack on Saudi oil fields in 2019. These events disrupted oil production without corresponding reductions in demand, driving up prices. Demand-side shocks, on the other hand, are influenced by global economic movements. For example, the economic growth in China and other developing economies significantly increased oil demand without a matching supply increase, leading to high oil prices. Conversely, during the 2007-2009 global financial crisis, a dramatic reduction in oil demand led to a collapse in oil prices (Filis, 2017).

Kilian (2009) identifies three types of oil price shocks: supply-side shocks, aggregate demand shocks, and precautionary demand shocks. Geopolitical unrest often triggers precautionary demand shocks, causing uncertainty about future oil availability and driving up prices. For instance, geopolitical events lead economic agents to expect shortages in oil supply, which results in high oil prices.

According to Salisu and Oloko (2015), crude oil price shocks affect exchange rates through the terms of trade and wealth effect channels. A negative oil price shock transforms wealth from oil exporters to importers, leading to higher production costs and inflation, which adversely affects trade balances. To improve trade balance, the exchange rate must adjust. The relationship between exchange rates and oil prices can differ between advanced and emerging market economies (Salisu & Oloko, 2015).

2.1.2 Exchange Rate and Stock Market Returns

Aruori (2011) emphasized that the relationship between the movement of exchange rate and stock returns could be explained with several perspectives. The flow-oriented model of exchange rate behaviour posits that depreciation in the exchange rate for instance would lead to improved trade balance as exports become cheaper. This would result in upward shift in aggregate demand (AD), hence overall expansion in real gross domestic product with the attendant positive effect on stock market performance. The stock-oriented model, on the other hand, emphasizes the role of capital accounts in the determination of a country's exchange rate. In this theory, the exchange rate equates the demand and supply of financial assets (stock and bonds). Thus, expectation of future exchange rates affects the current price of financial markets (Aruori, 2011). From another perspective Brown & Yucel, (2002) aligning with the arbitrage price theory argued that a rise in real interest rate will reduce the present value (PV) of the future cash flow which consequently make stock returns to fall. According to Brown & Yucel (2002) as the real interest rate rises, capital flows increase, causing the domestic currency to appreciate. This will in turn lead to a fall in stock returns.

2.1.3 Oil Price and Stock Price

Oil price may impact stock performance through several channels such as uncertainty, fiscal, output and stock variation channels (Degiannakis, Filis & Arora, 2018). Oil price is susceptible to high volatility due to supply shocks and therefore, the risk of uncertainties occasioned by oil price volatility usually affect investors' portfolio, particularly, portfolio managers seeking to make optimal portfolio allocations (Arouri, 2011); cited in Salisu and Oloko (2015). Also, Uncertainty channels views explain that rising crude oil prices heightens uncertainty in the real economy (firms and households) due to its effect on inflation, consumption, and output (Brown & Yucel, 2002). For a firm, it tends to reduce the demand for irreversible investment and consequently, expected cash flow declines. On the household, increased uncertainty, resulting from higher cost of crude oil also increases the households' ability to save rather than consume. (Brown & Yucel, 2002).

Given the above, the value of postponing investment and consumption decisions rises and hence, economic growth and stock market returns stifles. Oil prices also impact stock performance through a more direct channel—that is, the stock variation channel. The nexus suggests that stock returns are impacted by factors that can alter expected cash flows and discount rates. However, this depends on whether the firm is an oil user or oil producer. Given that oil is a major production factor, any increase in oil price will result in an increased production cost (assuming a case of absence of substitution effect between production factors). This leads to reduced profit levels and future cash flows. For the oil producer, increase in crude oil prices results in increased profit margins and thus, increased future cash flows (Basher & Sadosky, 2006). Furthermore, higher interest rate response by the monetary authority to an inflationary pressure from the rising oil prices also affect the discount rate; an important factor in stock price formulation (Basher, Haug & Sadosky, 2012)

2.2 Theoretical Review

Theory-based framework from various ideas have been used in the past to support analyses of the impact of oil price volatility on stock markets. As a result, the theoretical foundation for this study comes from the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT).

2.2.1 Theory of Arbitrage Pricing Arbitrage Pricing Theory (Apt)

The Arbitrage Pricing Theory is a multi-factor asset pricing model which assumes that an asset's returns may be forecasted using a linear relationship between the assets expected return and several other macroeconomic variables that influence risk. Stephen Ross, an American economist, created this idea in 1976. The APT provides a multi-factor pricing model for securitized assets to analysts and investors. The APT provides analysts and investors with a multi-factor pricing model for securities that is based on the link between the projected return of a financial asset and its risk characteristics. The goal of the arbitrage pricing theory (APT) is to determine the fair market price of a security that has been temporarily mispriced. The Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) is a more flexible and complicated alternative to the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM). The theory allows investors and analysts to tailor their studies to their specific needs. Arbitrage is the practice of the simultaneous purchase and sale of an asset on different exchanges, taking advantage of slight pricing discrepancies to lock in a risk-free profit for the trade. The arbitrage pricing theory provides traders with a model for calculating an asset's theoretical fair market value. Having determined that value, traders then look for slight deviations from the fair market price and trade accordingly. For example, if the APT pricing model determines the fair market value of a company's stock to be 50NGN, but the market price drops to 45NGN, the trader will buy the shares in the idea that additional market price action will rapidly "correct" the market price back to 50NGN/share. Thus, this study uses the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) to link crude oil prices and other selected macroeconomic variables (such as the exchange rate, inflation rate, and interest rate) to stock market performance in Nigeria from 1981 to 2019. Its theoretical underpinning is derived from the APT.

2.2.2 Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM)

The capital asset pricing model was pioneered by notable authors including Sharpe (1964), Umer (1965), Mossin (1960). The CAPM is a single factor model, quantifies the expected rates of return of an asset with level of market systematic risk. The CAPM has variously been lead among others by Chen (2003) and Kim et al. (a) 2017. It is a finance model that establishes a linear relationship between the required return on an investment and risk. CAPM evolved to measure this systematic risk. It is widely used throughout finance for pricing risky securities and generating expected returns for assets, given the risk of those asset and cost of capital.

Algebra, the Capital Assets Model is presented as

$$R_i = R_f + \beta_i (R_m - R_f) \quad 2.1$$

Where: R_m = market portfolio, R_m = Expected return on portfolio
 R_f = risk free return, R_i = Return on asset

$$\beta_i = \frac{COV (R_i, R_M)}{\sigma^2 M} \quad 2.2$$

β_i is called the beta of the asset i and σ^2_m is the variance of the market portfolio. For any portfolio $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n)$ of risky assets, its beta can be constructed as a weighted average of individual asset betas as follows: $E(r_d) = RFR + \beta \lambda (R_M) - RFR$ 2.3

$$\beta \lambda = \sum_{i=1}^P \alpha_i \beta_i \quad 2.4$$

The Beta value indicates a measure of risk for individual assets/portfolio. It measures the non-diversifiable or transferable part of risk known as systematic risk. According to this model, the expected return of an asset depends on its stand-alone risk. However, the CAPM has unrealistic assumptions for example, the perfect competitive market environment does not hold as forces of demand and supply often guide investors decision making as they

affect prices of assets. Also, tax liabilities affect the level of investment and the time of asset to invest in. the model also assume that at the risk-free rate, borrowing will be unlimited however, individual investors cannot borrow at the same rate will government and its agencies.

2.2.3 The Discount Cash Flow Model (DCF)

The relationship between oil price shocks and stock market return can also be theoretically explored or viewed through the discounted cash flow model (equity pricing model) developed by Huang et al (1996). The model has been adopted in several literature (Sek, 2015; Basher, 2014; Zakanya and Abdala, 2013; Abeng, 2017; Degiannakis, 2017). According to this model, macroeconomic variables including commodity prices can exert a significant effect on stock returns of firms. According, the price of equity at a given point in time is equal to the expected present value of the discounted future cash flows as follows

Where: P = Stock price, C = cash flow, r = Discount rate (interest rate), $E(1)$ = expectation operator. The realized stock returns R can be expressed approximately as

Where $d(\cdot)$ is the difference operator. Stock returns, R , are determined by the systematic movements in expected cash flows and discount rates, which can be affected by changes in oil prices in several ways. For cash flows, it is assumed that oil, together with labour. Capital and other inputs, represents import components in the production friction of most goods and services. Therefore, changes in the prices of these inputs including oil, affect cash flows of firms. i.e. rising oil prices increases production costs leading to dampened cash flows which ultimately translates to a reduction in stock prices. It however depends on whether a particular firm is a net producer or net consumer of oil. The discounted rate can also be affected by oil prices changes. According to Huang et al (1996), expected discount rate consists of two components; expected inflation and expected real interest rate. Higher oil prices will lead to a negative effect the trade balance in oil importing economics. Imposing upward pressure on domestic prices (inflation) which leads to higher discount rate culminating in lower stock returns. As an important resource in the economy, oil prices can affect real interest rates. High oil price is expected to raise the rates of real interest rates which may likely lead to increases in stock returns.

2.3 Empirical Review

In a study of 22 emerging economies (Nigeria not included), Maghyereh and Al-Kandari (2004) findings implied that oil shocks have no significant impact on stock index returns in emerging economies. Agren (2006) argued that the stock market's own shocks, which are related to other factors of uncertainty than the oil price, are more prominent in explaining stock price movements.

Similarly, in Ghana, findings by Adjasi (2009) showed that higher volatility in Cocoa prices and interest rates increased volatility of the stock prices, whilst higher volatility in gold prices, oil prices, and money supply reduced volatility of stock prices. Other studies, however, found the existence of a weak relationship among the variables. For instance, Sujit and Kumar (2011) evaluated the dynamic relationship among gold price, oil price, exchange rate and stock market returns. The authors used daily data from January 2, 1998, to June 5, 2011, constituting 3,485 observations and adopted the vector autoregressive and cointegration techniques. The results showed that exchange rate was highly affected by changes in the other variables, while stock market plays a minor role in affecting the exchange rate. The study suggested that there is weak long-term relationship among the variables.

Also, Sahu, Bandopadhyay, and Mondal (2015) investigated the dynamic relationships between oil price, exchange rate and the Indian stock market from 1993 – 2013. Results from the Johansen's cointegration test and vector error correction model showed that although there is a long run cointegrating relationships between crude

oil price and Indian stock indices, no sufficient evidence existed to conclude that the direction of the relationship in the long run was from oil price to the Sensex. However, the Granger causality test showed that the volatility of stock prices in India granger caused the movement in oil price and exchange rate in the short-run. The study further showed that the observed relationship between oil price and stock indices was not because of exchange rate fluctuations, because the change in exchange rate had no significant impact on oil prices or stock prices in India during the study period.

In Nigeria, attempts have also been made to examine the relationship among oil price, exchange rate and stock market returns. The findings from the study by Fowowe (2013) on the dynamic relationship between oil prices and stock market returns in Nigeria, using the GARCH-Jump model showed the existence of a negative, but insignificant effect of oil prices on stock returns in Nigeria.

Another study was conducted by Mechri, Ben Hamad, De Peretti and Chart (2018) on the impact of exchange rate volatilities on stock markets dynamics in Tunisia and Turkey, using the GARCH estimation method. The variables used were stock market price returns, exchange rates, inflation rates, interest rates, gold prices and petrol prices index. The results indicated that exchange rate volatility has a significant effect on stock market fluctuations.

Alzyoud, Wang and Basso (2018) also examined the dynamics of Canadian oil price and its Impact on Exchange Rate and Stock Market performance. The authors adopted the cointegration technique and used stock index, exchange rate, and crude oil price as variables in the study. The findings indicated that oil price, exchange rate, and their variations had a positive and significant impact on the Canadian stock market returns.

2.3.1 Trend Analysis in Oil Price and Stock Performance.

Before 2012, the movement of crude oil prices and the All Share Index (ASI) in Nigeria was inconsistent. As crude oil prices increased, stock behavior was often bearish, suggesting other factors influenced stock prices. From March 2012 to May 2014, the stock market was mostly bullish, with capital market indicators pushing positively except for a decline from June to September 2013 due to concerns over the US Federal Reserve's adjustment of its quantitative easing policy. This period saw higher and stable crude oil prices and increased economic activities. However, during the recession in Nigeria from September 2014 to April 2017, both the ASI and crude oil prices declined significantly (Iyoha, 2017).

Despite the recession, the Nigerian stock market was listed among the best performing globally. The NSE ASI increased by 47.19% and crossed the 38,000 points mark by the end of the year, driven by strong corporate earnings from blue-chip companies, increased capital inflow, and portfolio investments (Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review, December 2020). In 2014, the market started positively, but activities turned bearish due to foreign investors' withdrawal, currency risks, and the recovery of developed economies. The bearish sentiment worsened in the second half of 2014 due to the global economic recession, which saw crude oil prices crash from \$110 to \$40 per barrel. Attacks on oil installations by militants in the Niger Delta region led to a loss of about one million barrels of crude oil exports per day, further impacting the stock market. Other macroeconomic factors, such as declining foreign reserves and weak corporate earnings, contributed to the market's decline. Investors adopted a 'flight to quality' strategy amidst the uncertainty (Salisu & Oloko, 2015).

In 2015, the bearish trend continued, with the NSE ASI falling by 17.4% to 28,642 points by year-end. The market's poor performance was due to political risk, currency volatility, and uncertainty in global crude oil prices. This bearish trend persisted into 2016, with the stock market recording a 16.05% loss in January. However, in

May 2016, the market saw a slight improvement with a 0.38% gain, the highest monthly gain that year. By December 19, 2016, the market recorded a 5.33% gain, but the NSE ASI remained negative on most trading days, ending the year with an 18.0% year-to-date loss. In 2017, the market gradually recovered from the economic recession, with the NSE ASI index increasing by 42.0%, making it the third best-performing market globally. This improvement was partly due to the Central Bank's monetary policies that increased liquidity in the foreign exchange market.

In 2018, as the Nigerian economy continued its recovery, the NSE equities market started strongly, with the ASI reaching a ten-year peak of 45,092.83 in January. However, the market began to decline in the second quarter, with the ASI falling by 17.81% to 31,430.50 points by year-end. Macroeconomic factors, including political risks, oil price volatility, and rising global yields, contributed to the bearish sentiment. In the first half of 2019, market sentiments were driven by uncertainty in oil prices and the 2019 general elections. Post-election stability dampened the volatility in the equities market. With the approval and implementation of the 2019 budget, positive impacts on company earnings and consumer spending were expected to boost market activity in the second half of 2019. These periods also experienced higher and stable crude oil prices and increased economic activities (Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review, December 2020).

For the purpose of this study, a simple stock return series is specified as a function of exchange rate and crude oil price: $ASI = f(ER, P)$, where ER is the Bureau-de-Change exchange rate and P is the crude oil price. To determine if volatility in these series matters more than the crude oil price and exchange rate return series themselves, a variation of this equation is specified such that the All Share Index is a function of the volatilities in crude oil price and exchange rate: $ASI = g(s)$.

METHODOLOGY

3.1.1 Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT)

The arbitrage pricing theory was developed by Stephen Ross in 1976. The arbitrage pricing theory is a general theory of asset pricing that holds that the expected returns of a financial asset can be modeled as a linear function of various macroeconomic factors or theoretical market indices, where the sensitivity to change in each factor is represented by a factor specific beta coefficient (Alexander, Sharpe, and Bailey, 2001). The model's derived rate of return will then be used to price the financial asset correctly; this asset price should be equal to the expected end of period return discounted at the rate implied by the model. In an event that the prices diverge then arbitrage actions should bring the price back to its correct level. APT assumes that asset returns are related to an unknown number of macroeconomic factors (Alexander, Sharpe, and Bailey, 2001). The model attributes the expected return of a capital asset multiple risk factors, and in the process measures the risk premiums associated with each of these risk factors. Arbitrage Pricing Theory addresses the question of whether the risk associated with the macroeconomic variable is reflected in the expected market returns.

According to (Chen, Roll, & Ross, 1986), economic variables have a systematic consequence on stock market returns because economic forces affect discount rates, the ability of the firm to generate cash and future dividend payments. The core idea of APT is that only a small number of systematic influences affect the long-term average returns of securities.

3.2 Method of Analyses

GARCH model was employed in measuring the volatility in exchange rate, oil prices, inflation and interest rate using the GARCH as developed by Robert (1982). The approach to estimate volatility in financial markets; we

can think of heteroskedasticity as time-varying variance (i.e., volatility). Conditional implies a dependence on the observations of the immediate past, and autoregressive describes a feedback mechanism that incorporates past observations into the present. GARCH then is a mechanism that includes past variances in the explanation of future variances. More specifically, GARCH is a time series modeling technique that uses past variances and past variance forecasts to forecast future variances. The principal method employed to analyze the time series behavior of the data involves unit root test, co-integration test, normality test, heteroskedasticity, and the estimation of an error correction model (ECM). Specifically, we employ unit root test to detect the order of integration of the variables using the Dickey Fuller and Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test by dickey And fuller (1979) The unit root test is necessary because research has shown that non-stationary data leads to spurious regression. We employ Co- integration test to examine whether there is long-run co-movement in the variable using the Engle and granger two stage technique. The ECM measures the short run dynamic adjustments towards long run equilibrium. We commence by testing for unit root in the data. The first step is to determine the order of integration of the variables before testing for co-integration.

3.2.1 Model Specification

To examine the impact of macroeconomic variables on stock return in Nigeria, a model anchored on the theory as used by Ray, (2012) is adapted as follows.

$$ASI = f(CPI, IP, MS, EXCH) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

Where ASI represents stock market performance, CPI represents consumer price index, IP represents industrial production, MS represents money supply and EXCH represents exchange rate while f represents the functional relationship. However, the model is modified to INTR, INFL, OILP, and INV as in equation 3.2.

$$ASI = f(EXCH, INTR, INFL, OILP, RGDP) \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

The reason for the inclusion of oil price as one of the explanatory variables and variable of interest is that. It is said that increase in oil price lead to an appreciation of the naira as more foreign currencies are generated through improved oil revenue as further shown by growth in value of oil export as a percentage of total export. However, contrary to expectation Nigeria, an oil exporting country still experiences the golden rule- “oil up, stock down” which should be applicable to oil importing countries. This may be an indication the country’s failure to translate its huge foreign exchange earnings from oil into an improved industrial sector productivity. It also an indirect manifestation of the deleterious effect of huge annual foreign exchange expenditure on importation of petrol/diesel for energy supply bothering on the inability to locally refine a substantial part of its crude oil and the apparent collapse of power supply by the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) for domestic and industrial use. It is recommended that the most viable solution towards improved economic performance lies in refining the Nigerian crude oil locally so that the huge benefits of the naturally endowed oil can be realized rather for the development of the economies of other nations.

Also, the inclusion of investment as control variable, it is simply because there is a close relation between the stock market and investment. That is fluctuations in the stock market can affect investment of firms. The relationship between stock market prices and firms’ investment in physical capital is captured by the “q theory of investment”, developed by James Tobin (1969). That is, an increase in the prospective return on capital or a decrease in the market’s discount rate raises q and thereby increases investment. With a simple form of adjustment cost for changing the capital stock, the optimal amount of current investment depends only on the current value of q.

Definition of Variables

The variables used in the model are defined below: -

- i. **Dependent Variable** ASI = All Shares index
- ii. **Independent Variables:** EXCH = Exchange Rate, INTR = Interest Rate, INFL = Inflation, OILP = Oil Price, RGDP = Real GDP

Expressing equation 3.2 in linear form yields equation 3.3.

$$ASI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EXCH_1 + \beta_2 INTR_2 + \beta_3 INFL_3 + \beta_4 OILP_4 + \beta_5 RGDP_5 \dots \dots \dots (3.3)$$

Where $\beta_0 = \text{constant}$ β_1 to β_5 represents various slope coefficients while EXCH, INTR, INFL, OILP and RGDP remain as defined above. Putting the variables in the same scale of measurement and adding the stochastic disturbance term yields equation 3.4

$$LASI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LEXCH_1 + \beta_2 LINTR_2 + \beta_3 LINFL_3 + \beta_4 LOILP_4 + \beta_5 LRGDP_5 + \mu \dots \dots \dots (3.3)$$

Where, L represent the natural log of the variables. This is necessary to avoid large fluctuation in the variables. All other variables remain as defined above. On a-priori $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_5 > 0$ and $\beta_4 > \text{or} < 0$ Exchange rates supposed to have positive relationship with stock market: due to globalization, businesses are affected either directly or indirectly by international trade activities.

3.2.2 Data Analysis

Research has shown that most time series data poses unit root i.e. they are not stationary. Thus, research carried out with them is likely to be spurious or non-sense. A test of stationarity in time series data is very important because since the 1970s, macroeconomic aggregates in Nigeria have been fluctuating greatly. The consequence of using non stationarity is so grave that well established models are breaking down as they continuously fail to predict outcomes. The problem according to Granger and Newbold, (1974) is that regression results on non-stationarity series may, most times be “spurious or nonsensical” to the extent that a relationship would be accepted as existing between two variables as measured by their co-efficient of determination when in fact no relationships exist. Inference from non — stationary time series apart from being spurious, violate the classical econometric assumption, thus making the result unreliable for policy making. Also, pre-estimation test such as unit root tests and cointegration test were carried out while, post estimation tests such as stability test, normality test, auto correlation test etc. were also carried out to establish the consistency and reliability of the models adopted in this study.

● Unit Root/Stationarity Test

Adopting the Engel — Granger (1987) and Engel and Yule, (1987), we proceed to modeling a framework by first testing for stationarity To provide a more definitive answer to the non-stationarity, in each time series, the Dickey – Fuller (1979) regression is estimated as follows for unit root.

$$\Delta Y_t = \lambda Y_{t-1} + V_t \dots \dots \dots (3.5)$$

If λ equals 0, Y_t is non-stationary, as a result Y_t and X_t are not co-integrated. In other words, if λ is significantly different from 0 Y_t and X_t are found integrated individually. Given the inherent weakness of the unit root to distinguish between null and the alternative hypotheses, it is desirable that the augmented Dickey — Fuller (ADF), 1981 test be applied. To be co-integrated; both Y_t and X_t must have the same order of integration (Engel and Granger, 1987, and Granger, 1986).

The ADF regression is specified as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \delta Y_{t-1} + \gamma_i \sum_{t=1}^m \Delta Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots\dots (3.6)$$

Δ is the first difference operator, ε_t is the new random error term, M is the optimum number of lags needed to obtain “white noise”. This is approximated when the DW values approaches 2.0 numerically. The null hypothesis of non-stationarity is rejected if the estimated ADF statistic is found to be larger in absolute term or more negative than its critical values at 1 or 5 percent level of significance.

● Concept of Co-integration

Co-integration among the variables is used to determine the existence of a long run equilibrium relationship between the variables. The concept of co-integration (Granger, 1986, Mill 1990) creates the link between integrated processes and the concept of steady state equilibrium. The idea behind co-integration is that ‘although two different series may not themselves be stationary, some linear combination of them may be indeed stationary with the generalization to more than two series’ (Komolafe, 1996). Economic variables are inherently non-stationary and thus, could meander without any tendency to return to equilibrium in the long run. Implicit in the co-integration theory is the fact that there exists a linear combination of these non-stationary variables that is stationary.

The traditional approach to the modeling of short-run disequilibrium is the partial adjustment method. However, an extension of this in the co-integration technique is the Error correction mechanism (ECM) (Granger and Newbold, 1977). The original co-integration relationship is specified as follows:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3.7)$$

Analyzing the long-run behavior of Y_t implies investigating co-integrating relationship in (1). If μ_t is stationary then, the $I(1)$ variable in X_t may be thought of as capturing the long run component of Y_t while E_t captures the short run or temporary movements.

● Error correction technique

If the Y_t and X_t are found to be co-integrated, then there must exist an associated Error Correction Model (ECM), according to Engel and Granger (1987). The usual ECM may take the following form.

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \sum_{t=1}^m \Delta X_{t-1} + \delta_i \sum_{t=1}^m \Delta Y_{t-1} + \gamma_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \psi_t \dots\dots\dots (3.8)$$

Where, Δ denotes first difference operators, ε_{t-1} is the error correction term, m is the number of lags necessary to obtain “white noise” and ψ_t is another random disturbance term. If $|\delta|$ is significantly different from zero, then Y_t and X_t will have longer run relationship. The (ECM) error correction term (ε_{t-1}) depicts the extent of disequilibrium between Y_t and X_t . the ECM, reveals further that the change in Y_t not only depend on lagged changes in x_t but also on its own lagged changes. The estimate of the parameters of the ECM are generally consistent and efficient (Hendry and Richard, 1983). Inference about the long run Granger causality can be drawn from the ECM model. The presence of co integration will indicate at least, unidirectional long run causality from ΔX_{t-j} , if statistically significant will indicate a short run causality from ΔX_{t-j} , to ΔY_{t-j} . The statistically significant non-Zero co-efficient of ΔY_{t-j} will indicate feedback to ΔY_t from its own lagged values. It may be noted that even in the absence of co-integration, the error correction model may be estimated to detect if there is any short run granger causality.

3.2.3 Nature and Sources of Data

The data used in the study are collected from various publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria and (CBN), World Development Indicator (WDI), National Bureau of statistic (NBS). Specifically, the data used are time series data, which includes the exchange rate (EXCH), interest rate (INTR), inflation (INFL), oil price (OILP) and Real GDP(RGDP)

3.2.4 Criteria for Model Evaluation

To analyse the model, we employed the economic criteria which is used to measure the sign and size of the parameters in the model.

Statistical Criteria: This includes the T-statistic, F-statistic, and R^2

Co-efficient of determination (R^2)

Coefficient of determination also known as R square (R^2) or goodness of fit tells the proportion of the total variable in the dependent variable y that is explained by the regression line or the explanatory variables x. in a single / simple regression model, it is the square of the correlation coefficient in a simple regression model. The value of the R^2 lies between 0 and 1 i.e. $0 \leq R^2 \leq 1$ when the $R^2 = 0$, it means the explanatory variable do not explain the dependent variable and when the $R^2 = 1$, it means the model is best fit. If the R^2 is multiplied by 100, then it shows the percentage of total variation in y the dependent variable that is explained by variation / changes in x. the closer the R^2 is to one. The stronger is the explanatory power of the estimated regression line, and thus the closer are the observation to the line. If $R^2 = 0.56$ it means that 56% of total variation in y is explained by the regression line / changes in x and the other 44 remains unexplained by x

Test of individual statistics of the slope coefficient (T. Test)

This tests the individual significance of the co-efficient, to do this, we test the null hypothesis that $b_i = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis that $b_i \neq 0$ in employing the t test, we compare the computed t-value with the value read from the student's t table at given level of significance, (α) and n-k degree of freedom/ if the absolute value of the computed t value is greater than the absolute value of the theoretical, t value, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) at the given level of significance i.e. if $t_{cal} > t_{tab}$, reject H_0 ; Accept H_1 $t_{cal} < t_{tab}$, Accept H_0 , reject H_1 . Alternatively, the rule of thumb can be used, which state that if the T_{cal} is greater than 2 at the 5 percent level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the parameter is statistically significant in explaining the dependent variables.

The F Statistic (Test for overall significance of the model)

This is used to test for the statistical significance of the entire slope coefficient jointly on the dependent variable using a level of significance. The F statistic is done by comparing the F_{cal} with the F tabulated. When the F_{cal} is greater than the F_{table} we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the entire variable put together is statistically significant in explaining the dependent variable.

3.2.4 Econometric Criteria

This includes the test for serial correlation.

D.W Statistic Durbin – Watson Test

It is the most popular test for serial/autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic is used to test the presence of serial correlation in a model, to determine whether there is serial correlation in the model, we compare the Durbin-Watson value from the model to the Durbin-Watson critical value at 5%. If the value of Durbin Watson lies between the upper limit and four minus upper limits (i.e. $4 - du < dw < 4 - du$), We reject the null hypothesis at the 5 percent level of significance and conclude that there is no autocorrelation (positive or negative autocorrelation) in the model.

Table 3.2.5: Definitions and Measurement of Variables

S/N	Variable	Symbol	Measurement
1	All Shares Index	ASI	Obtained by multiplying the price per share by the number of shares outstanding
2	Exchange Rate	EXCH	The price of one country's currency expressed in another country currency
3	Inflation Rate	INFL	The rate of inflation reported in CBN Statistical Bulletin
4	Interest Rate	INTR	An accrued amount that includes principal plus interest
5	Real Gross Domestic Product	RGDP	Real Gross Domestic product
6	Oil Prices	OILP	The price of bulk oil, usually quoted in US dollars per barrel

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

4.1 Presentation of Results

4.1.1 Trend Analysis

In this section, graphical illustrations of the various variables that were used within the time period to see their direction were conducted and this helps to show whether they are increasing or not and also see their cyclical pattern. Thus, a graphical sketch of each of the variable over time was made.

Figure 1: Trend of Inflation in Nigeria

Source: Author's computation using Microsoft Excel (2021)

The trend of inflation as shown in years 1986-1996 was very high as compared to the other years. From 1987-2020 it is below the trend line and fluctuating at a stable rate. For instance, in the year 1986, 1987, the inflation shoots out skyrocketingly over the period. Also, from 1992 to 1997, it was revealed that it went up so high, however, at this point lots of activities may be distorted as a result of an increase in inflation, because it will bring about unemployment, high price of goods and services. More so, it was also observed that from 2000 to 2020 the inflation is practically and steadily volatile during the period under investigation.

Figure 2. Trend of oil Price in Nigeria

Source: Author's computation using Microsoft Excel (2021)

Figure 2 shows the trend of oil price in Nigeria and the trend line pattern during period under investigation. As it can be seen above that oil prices were stagnant for some years and it skyrocketed for some years and went back to the initial price before it skyrocketed. This can be as a result of demand and supply. This suggests that oil price has a very significant impact on stock market performance. Hence, in the year 1994 to 1997, also, 2000 to 2003 and from this point, there was a consistent with the trend, however, 2008 2012 till 2020 the oil price is practically fluctuating over the period under review which is capable of incapacitated the growth of the economy.

Figure 3. Trend of Interest Rate in Nigeria

Source: Author's computation using Microsoft Excel (2021)

According to Figure 3 above, interest rates continuously grow while experiencing high levels of volatility. For instance, the interest rate was below average from 1986 to 1992, which can cause the economy's activities to change in response to even the smallest shock. While the interest rate was above normal from 1993 to 1995, it was much below average from 1996 to 1999. Additionally, the interest rate was above average from 2000 to 2010

and below average from 2011 to 2020. This is a sign that Nigeria's interest rates are very low because they do not promote private consumption or the expansion and improvement of the country's whole economy.

Figure 4. Trend of Real GDP in Nigeria

Source: Author’s computation using Microsoft Excel (2021)

From 1986 to 2020, the actual gross domestic output is shown in Figure 4. Over the years, the real GDP has remained somewhat stable and has been relatively high. It has been increasing at a stable rate and rarely is there any big shock or fluctuation. More so, the gross domestic product is varying across the years under examination, it reveals there is an upward tendency between 1986-1992, and somewhat steady till 1995 subsequently there is a constant movement upward till 2015, 2015-2020 stays slightly stable. This also suggests that the gross domestic product practically varied during the time under investigation, which will undoubtedly have a negative impact on the expansion and development of the Nigerian economy.

Figure 5. Trend of Exchange Rate

Source: Author’s computation using Microsoft Excel (2021)

As seen in figure 5 above, the exchange rate was essentially volatile and fluctuated during the time under consideration. From 1986 to 1996, it was essentially zigzagging and varied frequently, but it was still somewhat

steady. However, starting in 1997, it was no longer stable. Particularly between 2000 and 2020, it was extremely volatile. Of course, this can negatively impact Nigeria's stock market performance. This also implies that, if serious action is not taken in Nigeria, this trend may have an impact on economic growth and development.

Figure 6: Trend of Domestic Financing

Source: Author's computation using Microsoft Excel (2021)

Figure 6 shows the level of All Shares Index in Nigeria and the trendline pattern during period under the investigation. As it can be seen above that All Shared Index was fluctuating frequently for the periods, at some points All Shares Index was above trendline while other time was below trendline, which makes the capital market practically unstable. This will in turn affect the growth and development of the entire economy at large

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

The variables utilised in the study are described and analysed in this subsection. The purpose of descriptive statistics is to explain the historical context of the data's behaviour. The variables range from 1986 to 2020 and include gross domestic product, budget balance, tax revenue, current spending, capital spending, domestic financing, and foreign financing variables. Table 4.2.1 lists the descriptive data.

Table 4.2.1: Descriptive Statistics Estimate Result

Statistic	ASI	OILP	INF	INTR	RGDP	EXR
Mean	46.71429	23.08882	19.51429	18.73423	8.525468	18.68472
Median	44.00000	11.61643	12.55000	17.79500	8.700933	17.29843
Maximum	91.00000	88.00000	72.84000	31.65000	10.01416	78.00000
Minimum	12.00000	10.43900	5.390000	9.959167	6.373485	2.073963
Std. Dev.	24.40778	20.92982	17.82661	3.929100	0.948712	15.52646
Skewness	0.231483	1.705714	1.703099	0.951120	-0.406531	1.642480
Kurtosis	1.926956	4.762934	4.547639	5.147241	2.270349	7.138366
Jarque-Bera	1.991733	21.50427	20.41283	12.00086	1.740461	40.71234
Probability	0.369403	0.000021	0.000037	0.002478	0.418855	0.000000
Sum	1635.000	808.1088	683.0000	655.6980	298.3914	653.9652
Sum Sq. Dev.	20255.14	14893.95	10804.79	524.8862	30.60187	8196.408
Observations	35	35	35	35	35	35

Source: Author's Computation, 2022

Table 4.2.1 provides the summary statistics for these variables, including averages, medians, maximum and minimum values for the time period. The vast discrepancy between the minimum and highest values for the

variables under investigation appears to be indicative of considerable variability. The remaining variables' standard deviations show that the data are closely clustered around the mean and therefore less volatile.

The descriptive result reveals that some variables are extremely volatile in nature and of course other variables are not volatile as such. It was observed from the result that, there is maximum and minimum, this is just to show the characteristics of the variables used as to know the nature of each variable as well the whole at large as it can be seen from the above Table. A test is carried out to show whether the distribution follow normality condition. If the probability value as presented in table 4.2.1 exceeds 5%, then the null hypothesis of normal distribution is accepted, otherwise the null hypothesis of normal distribution is rejected. All the distributions are positively skewed with the exception of real gross domestic product which is negatively skewed during the study period under investigation. Thus, on the other hand, kurtosis, which is an attribute of a dataset can be described using the statistical measure kurtosis. On a graph, regularly distributed data typically resembles an upside-down bell when plotted. The bell curve is a name for this. The tails on either side of the curve are often formed by the plotted data that are most dispersed from the data mean. Kurtosis reveals how much information is included in the tails and of course kurtosis which less than three are called platykurtic (fat or short-tailed) and ASI and RGDP qualified for this during the study period under review while the ones greater than three are OILP, INF INTR and EXR are qualified for this.

Table 4.2.2: Correlation Matrix Estimate Result

Correlation	ASI	OILP	INF	INTR	RGDP	EXR
ASI	1.000000	0.193874	-0.204483	-0.097872	0.059704	-0.008569
OILP		1.000000	-0.079885	0.220263	-0.061262	-0.100829
INF			1.000000	0.428757	-0.269735	-0.075939
INTR				1.000000	-0.362421	0.016981
RGDP					1.000000	-0.424718
EXR						1.000000

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

The results of the correlation matrix are shown in Table 4.2.2. The test is conducted to determine the type of relationship between the variables and their degree of causation. This is important to do in order to avoid the multicollinearity problem that could arise from a high correlation among the explanatory components. The conclusions thus demonstrate that there is a direct correlation between all the explanatory variables and the dependent variable, all shares index (ASI). Furthermore, there is a connection between the price of oil and real GDP, interest rates, inflation, and currency exchange rates. There is no reason for a strong association among the explanatory factors in terms of degree of causation. Results of the degree of causality, however, suggest that our study is free from the multicollinearity issue because there is only a weak correlation between the explanatory variables. The highest degree of relationship between the explanatory variables is 0.008 and is between real gross domestic product and budget balance, and it is not ideal because the correlation coefficient is not 1. This further demonstrates that there is no perfect correlation between the explanatory variables.

Table 4.2.3 Unit Root Test Estimate Result

Variable	Method	At Level			At First Difference			Order
		ADF statistics	5% critical value	Prob	ADF statistics	5% critical value	Prob	
ASI	ADF	0.537	-2.992	0.9845	-3.689*	-2.998	0.0115	I (1)
OILP	ADF	-5.483*	-3.691	0.0719	-5.456*	-1.587	-0.001	I (1)
INF	ADF	-4.483*	-2.992	0.5248	-	-	-	I (0)
INT	ADF	-0.063*	-1.959	0.6495	-7.483*	-1.957	0.0000	I (1)
RGDP	ADF	-1.573*	-3.005	0.4791	-3.408*	-3.005	0.0219	I (1)
EXR	ADF	-5.287*	-3.760	0.1061	-	-	-	I (0)

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

* Implies significant at 5% meaning that the variable is stationary at that order

** Implies significant at 1% meaning that the variable is stationary at that order

Table 4.2.3 reports the results of the stationarity tests at the level and first difference as well for all the variables. We include a constant and a trend term in these tests. The optimal lag length of each case for ADF tests is chosen using the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) after testing for higher order serial correlation residuals. It was reported from the above result that all shares index, oil price, inflation, interest rate, real gross domestic product and exchange rate were stationary at level and first differences, no further tests are performed thereof. Consequently, it can also be concluded that the variables used for this have different order of integration, that is, both at level I(0) and first difference I(1). Therefore, we can now proceed to Autoregressive Distributed Lag Models (ARDL) bound estimate to determine the variables long run cointegration level.

Table 4.2.4 ARDL Bounds Test Estimate Result

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	7.570974	10%	1.99	2.94
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		2.5%	2.55	3.61
		1%	2.88	3.99
Actual Sample Size	29		Finite Sample: n=35	
		10%	2.254	3.388
		5%	2.685	3.96
		1%	3.713	5.326
			Finite Sample: n=30	
		10%	2.334	3.515
		5%	2.794	4.148
		1%	3.976	5.691

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Table 4.2.4 above shows there is a long run relationship among the variables of the model. Decision rule: we compare the F-stat. to the critical values at both I(0) and I(1) bounds. When the f-stat. (7.570974) is greater than

bound critical values $I(0)$ at all the level of significance i.e. 1%, 2.5%, 5% and 10% levels; we can say here that co-integration exists among the variable. Since the f-stat. (7.570974) is greater than both lower bound and upper bound the critical value at $I(0)$ or $I(1)$, this confirms the presence of co-integration. Thus, we therefore process to ARDL cointegration long run.

Table 4.2.5: ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form

Dependent Variable: ASI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(OILP)	0.295814	0.236466	1.250977	0.0225
D(INF)	-0.574141	0.336823	-1.704581	0.0007
D(INTR)	-1.273865	1.501326	-0.848493	0.0042
D(RGDP)	2.235216	6.518543	-0.342901	0.0345
D(EXR)	-0.005565	0.331913	-0.016766	0.0068
CointEq(-1)	-0.947589	0.194724	-4.866329	0.0001

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{ASI} - (-0.0475*\text{OILP} - 0.1404*\text{INF} - 1.3443*\text{INTR} + 2.3588*\text{INV} - 0.0059*\text{EXR} + 96.9681)$$

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
OILP	0.047514	0.287384	-0.165332	0.0000
INF	-0.140435	0.352857	-0.397995	0.0040
INTR	-1.344323	1.534881	-0.875848	0.0295
RGDP	2.358845	6.816926	-0.346028	0.0322
EXR	-0.005873	0.350250	-0.016767	0.0468
C	96.968089	78.937078	1.228423	0.0010

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Table 4.2.6 gives an insight of the nexus among the variables used for this study. Thus, as it can be seen below, the granger causality test result.

4.2.6: Granger Causality Estimation Test

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
OILP does not Granger Cause ASI	33	0.59244	0.5598
ASI does not Granger Cause OILP		0.43586	0.6510
INF does not Granger Cause ASI	33	2.12874	0.1378
ASI does not Granger Cause INF		1.13147	0.3369
INTR does not Granger Cause ASI	33	0.21232	0.8100
ASI does not Granger Cause INTR		0.64591	0.5318
RDGP does not Granger Cause ASI	33	0.16178	0.8514
ASI does not Granger Cause RDGP		0.33014	0.7216
EXR does not Granger Cause ASI	33	0.18446	0.8326
ASI does not Granger Cause EXR		0.41617	0.6636

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

From the Table 4.2.6 reveal the granger causality of the variables for the period under review spanning from 1986 to 2020. This is to find the nexus among the variables used for this study.

4.3 Post Diagnostic Estimate Result

Table 4.3.1: Normality Estimate Test Result

The results of the normalcy test are displayed in Table 4.3.1 above. We accept the null hypothesis that the model of this study is normal because the probability value (0.472139) exhibits insignificance. The model is thus verified to be suitable for estimate. This further implies that the model's estimation is a good fit for the investigation.

Table 4.3.2: Estimation of Serial Correlation Test Result

F-statistic	0.166956	Prob. F(2,23)	0.8473
Obs*R-squared	0.486547	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.7841

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

It is insignificant, as shown by the correlation value from Table 4.3.2 above. Given that the study's variables span a period of 35 years, it follows that we accept the null hypothesis that there is no link between them. The lack of correlation demonstrates that the study's data are accurate and suitable for estimation. Data must be devoid of correlation because if correlation occurs in the data used for the analysis, the outcome could be erroneous.

Table 4.3.3: Estimation of Heteroskedasticity Test Result

F-statistic	0.714066	Prob. F(8,25)	0.6771
Obs*R-squared	6.324001	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.6110
Scaled explained SS	1.743607	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.9879

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Table 4.3.3 above on the other hand, also revealed the estimation of the heteroskedasticity result of the variables used for the study. Thus, it was noted that the model does not exhibit any iota of heteroskedasticity. This simply suggests that, the estimation is accurate and suitable for the analysis.

Akaike Information Criteria (top 20 models)

The best ARDL model is chosen based on the minimum Akaike information value. The illustration above demonstrates that the ideal delay length is the ARDL order (1, 1, 0, 0). As shown above.

4.4: Discussion of Results

The above Table 4.2.5 discusses the results outcome according to the objectives earlier stated in the chapter one. This result provides answer to objective one and three:

Objective one: the impact of oil price volatility on stock market returns in Nigeria. To achieve this stated objective, our result from ARDL model regression will provide profound an empirical answer to the objective. Thus, oil price (OILP), is positive and statistically significant at 5% level of significance. This indicates that a unit increase in oil prices will eventually lead to 0.295814 increase in stock market performance in the short run, at the same time, it was equally observed from the outcome that oil price also positive and statistically significant in the long run. It equally suggests that one percent increase in oil price will bring about 0.047514 increase in stock market performance in Nigeria during the period under investigation. This result also corroborates with the study by Alamgir and Amin, (2021) who examined the nexus between oil price and stock market, and it was found out that, there is positive relationship between the oil price and stock market index, and the response of the stock market index to positive.

Second objective is to also determine effect of oil price fluctuation on the economic growth in Nigeria. To achieve the two objectives, we investigate the coefficient and p-value from above Table 4.2.5, however, it was revealed from the outcome that the real gross domestic product is positively and statistically significant at 5% level of

significance. This suggests that both short and long, it was observed that a unit rise in real gross domestic product (which is economic growth) will bring about 2.235216 and 2.358845 increase in oil price in both short and long run respectively. Thus, this study's outcome undoubtedly corroborates with the study by Erdem, Gozbasi, Ilgun and Nazlioglu, (2010) who investigated stock market and economic growth nexus in emerging markets, with findings that there is a close relationship between stock market performance and economic growth in the long-run and that stock market performance is an impetus for economic growth in the short-run.

The third objective is to ascertain the nexus between oil price volatility and stock market returns: To achieve this, the outcome of granger causality test result from the Table 4.2.6 will salvage this. Thus, the granger causality estimate indicates that oil price (OILP) does granger caused all shares index (ASI), while OILP does not granger caused ASI. We therefore accept the hypothesis that oil price does granger caused all shares performance and we fail to accept the hypothesis that ASI does granger caused OILP. This suggests that there is a unidirectional relationship exist between budgeting and economic growth in Nigeria. This equally suggest that an increase in oil price will definitely amount to a rise in all shares performance in Nigeria.

The result above also, reveals the inflation (INF) does granger caused stock market performance (ASI), whereas stock market performance does not granger caused inflation. Owing to this fact, we fail to accept the hypothesis that inflation does granger caused stock market performance, and accept the hypothesis that ASI does not granger caused INF. This indicates that, there is a unidirectional found for ASI and INF in Nigeria during the period under investigation.

The result equally, shows that the interest rate (INTR) does granger caused ASI, while ASI does not granger caused INTR. On this note, we fail to accept the hypothesis that INTR does granger caused ASI, and accept the hypothesis that ASI does not granger caused INTR. This implies that, there is a unidirectional found for INTR and ASI in Nigeria over the period under review.

Above result indicates that real gross domestic product (RGDP) does granger caused ASI, while ASI does not granger caused RGDP. On this note, we fail to accept the hypothesis that RGDP does granger caused ASI and accept the hypothesis that ASI does not granger caused RGDP. This implies that, there is a unidirectional found for RGDP and ASI in Nigeria during the period investigation.

The study further suggests that there is unidirectional causality which occurring from exchange rate (EXR) and stock market performance (ASI) which does not granger caused ASI does not granger caused EXR. On this note, we fail to accept the hypothesis that EXR does granger caused ASI and accept the hypothesis that ASI not granger caused EXR. This indicates that, there is a unidirectional found between EXR and ASI during the investigation of this research in Nigeria.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The findings are outlined in this section based on the research objectives guiding the study. The study findings revealed that the oil price volatility studied have a varying effect on the stock market returns/performance when they were regressed together their combined effect is significant given the p-value of all shares index equals 0.0000 which is less than 0.05 significance level used in this study. The oil price volatility have significant effect on the stock market Performance.

The findings on the first study objective on whether interest rate has an effect on the stock market performance in stock market return in Nigeria. Specifically, the study findings revealed that interest rate plays an important role in influencing the changes or variations of the stock market Performance in Nigeria.

Based on the second objective in this study seeking to determine whether inflation rate influences stock market, the study findings found out that inflation rate significantly influences stock market performance in Nigeria.

Based on the third objective in this study seeking to establish the impact of oil price stock market performance in Nigeria stock exchange, the study findings showed that oil price has significant impact on the stock market performance in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

Stock market has been identified as one of the agents of economic growth and development and one of the surest avenues in which investors can put their savings to work earning returns. It also provides an economic boost through creation of liquidity. However, several authors have noted some of the constraints to the successful operation of stock market in many countries including Nigeria inclusive. The outcome has prompted a plethora of research to this exciting topic. The empirical result obtained from the regression analysis also is suggestive of the fact that government fiscal policy does not play the expected or role desired role in stimulating growth of stock market and in order to faster pace of economic growth should consider policy changes that will speed development of stock markets and encourage equity investment by domestic and foreign investors, that is to remove tax, legal and regulatory barriers that inhibit equity investments. Countries do not need to go further and adopt interventionist policies such as tax incentives to encourage stock investment. By removing barriers to the free flow of capital, countries can let market forces work naturally to boost their economic growth and prosperity.

5.3 Recommendation

The study recommends the following based on the findings.

- The Nigeria government need to constantly review and proper checkmate the rate of volatility of oil price with adequate policies that will ensure the country is always cushioned against the external shocks like the credit crunch as well as oil crisis. To afford this, national policies as well as regulatory frameworks governing key sectoral reforms with large external dependencies need to be instituted like the imports of oil and machinery and foreign debts and loans. Concerted efforts between various governments as well as policy makers need to be grounded on the policy to drive crucial enablers of the country towards self-sustenance curbing heavy import impacting on our balance of payment problems. Such drivers on oil exploration, minerals and food security will go a long way in ensuring the shilling remain stable, inflation is tamed, interest rates do not skyrocket while exchange rate is controlled by the monetary authority.
- All brokerage firms and investment advisors need to conduct periodic research on oil price volatility and advise their clients accordingly on the best counters to invest in owing to the various influences by oil price volatility on the stock market performance. Such research needs to also be published for ease of access by the potential as well as existing investors. On findings of macroeconomic trends, the investment advisors an end brokerage firms need to seek redress from the relevant policy makers as well as institutions aimed at bringing stability for the well good of the stock investors. The Central Bank of Nigeria being the monetary authority in Nigeria need to constantly be reviewing the interest rate trends, inflation rates, exchange rate, oil prices as well as level investment by comparing them with the developed economies.
- Central Bank of Nigeria with help of government need to institute strong measures in place that govern the monetary policy of Nigeria geared towards ensuring a stable oil price volatility suitable to steer economic growth of Nigeria which directly impacts on the performance of stock market.

➤ The monetary regulations should further be benchmarked against the international best practices to bring stability on the oil price volatility to assure shareholders of maximum performance from their investment in the stock market in the various industries of Nigeria stock exchange.

REFERENCES

- Adu, D. A. (2012). Effect of Macroeconomic Variables on Stock Market Returns Ghana: An Analysis Using Arbitrage Pricing Model. Institute of Distance Learning, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi.
- African markets: Evidence from Ghana. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 10(4), 333- 349.
- Agren, M. (2006). Does oil price uncertainty transmit to stock markets? (No. 2006: 23). Working Paper. the Gulf Corporation Council countries?
- Akigbo, S. (2014). Macroeconomic uncertainty and conditional stock-price volatility in frontier
- Ahmad, A, U., Abdullah, A., Sulong Z., & Abdullahi, A, T,. (2015). Causal Relationship between Stock Market Returns and Macroeconomic Variables in Nigeria, *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, ISSN: 2279-0845, Volume 20, Issue 5, pages 74-96.
- Akigbo, S. (2014). Macroeconomic uncertainty and conditional stock-price volatility in frontier African markets: Evidence from Ghana. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 10(4), 333- 349.
- Ali, R., Haq, M, A, &Ullah, S,. (2015). Macroeconomic Indicators and Stock Market Development, *Developing Country Studies*, ISSN 2224-607X, Vol.5, No.9, pages 139-149.
- Arouri, M. E. H. (2011). Does crude oil move stock markets in Europe? A sector investigation. *Economic Modelling*, 28(4), 1716-1725.
- Arouri, M., & Rault, C. (2009). On the influence of oil prices on stock markets: Evidence from panel analysis in GCC countries. Arouri, M., & Rault, C. (2010). Oil prices and stock markets: What drives what in the Gulf.
- Babatunde, S. (2012). Oil prices, exchange rates and emerging stock markets. *Energy Economics*, 34(1), 227-24.
- Degiannakis, S., Filis, G., & Arora, V. (2018). Oil prices and stock markets: A review of the theory and empirical evidence. *Energy Journal*, 39(5).
- Bai, S., & Koong, K. S. (2018). Oil prices, stock returns, and exchange rates: Empirical evidence from China and the United States. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 44, 12-33.
- Basher S. A., Haug, A. A., & Sadorsky, P. (2012). Oil prices, exchange rates and emerging stock markets.

- Boyer, M. M., & Fillion, D. (2007). Common and fundamental factors in stock returns of Canadian oil and gas companies. *Energy economics*, 29(3), 428-453.
- Collin Read (2012). *The Efficient Market Hypothesisists: Bachelier, Samuelson, Fama, Ross, Tobin, and Shiller*. ISBN 9781137292216.
- Cong, R. G., Wei, Y. M., Jiao, J. L., & Fan, Y. (2008). Relationships between oil price shocks and stock market: An empirical analysis from China. *Energy Policy*, 36(9), 3544-3553.
- Corporation Council countries? Babatunde, S. (2012). Oil prices, exchange rates and emerging stock markets. *Energy Economics*, 34(1), 227-24.
- Degiannakis, S., Filis, G., & Arora, V. (2018). Oil prices and stock markets: A review of the theory and empirical evidence. *Energy Journal*, 39(5).
- Energy Economics, 34(1), 227-24 Basher, S. A., & Sadorsky, P. (2006). Oil price risk and emerging stock markets. *Global finance journal*, 17(2), 224-251.
- Brown, S. P., & Yucel, M. K. (2002). Energy prices and aggregate economic activity: An interpretative survey. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 42(2), 193-208.
- Fowowe, B. (2013). Jump dynamics in the relationship between oil prices and the stock market: Evidence from Nigeria. *Energy*, 56, 31 - 38.
- Kilian (2009). Oil and the macroeconomy since World War II. *Journal of political economy*, 91(2), 228- 248.
- Salisu, A. A., & Oloko, T. F. (2015), Modeling oil price-US stock nexus: A VARMA-BEKK-AGARCH approach. *Energy Economics*, 50, Elsevier (Science Direct) Retrieved from www.elsevier.com.
- Samuelson, Paul (1965). "Proof That Properly Anticipated Prices Fluctuate Randomly" *Industrial Management Review*. 6: 41–49.